

Bhagavad Gita: A Guide for Leaders

Paper Id : 18299 Submission Date : 04/11/2023 Acceptance Date : 11/11/2023 Publication Date : 15/11/2023
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10400993

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Abstract

"When doubts haunt me, when disappointments stare me in the face, and I see no one ray of hope on the horizon, I turn to Bhagavad-Gita and find a verse to comfort me; and I immediately begin to smile in midst of overwhelming sorrow. Those who mediate on Gita will derive fresh joy and new meaning from it every day."

- Mahatma Gandhi

There are many leadership theories existed given by renowned scholar but, through this paper I will try to connect Bhagavad Gita guide of leadership to modern contemporary theories. Bhagavad Gita guide of leadership include morally strong, ethically good, no self-admiration, how to enable someone to work for organization, how to increase morale of employees etc. The basic problem of any organization is to have a great leadership so, that organization work efficiently. Every small to large organization need a leadership to achieve their goals whether it is at village level, district level, state level, national level or at international level all need an efficient leadership. Bhagavad Gita act as a guide for leaders. In medieval times we have example of Shankaracharya, in modern times we have Swami Vivekananda, Bal Gangadhar Tilak, Mahatma Gandhi, Shri Aurobindo, Narendra Modi, in west we have T.S Eliot, Henry David Thoreau, Nikola Tesla etc. all are influenced by Bhagavad Gita. Bhagavad Gita is not a document related to a single trait it is way of life. It has mysticism, philosophical insights related to life, Eco theology. It is not a cultural document it is philosophical, ethical, moral, spiritual guide. The leadership aspect is only a small drop of huge ocean of the knowledge of Bhagavad Gita. In Bhagwat Gita a solution of mental trauma, mind conflicts, confusions, stress, it is a document which work as a therapy for the reader. In this paper we will analyse only a small aspect of leadership guide. The document will conclude by giving suggestion to current and future leaders the qualities which they can acquire from Gita for the efficient working of their organization. It will end by presenting Bhagavad Gita as always inspiring document for future generation.

Keywords

Bhagavad Gita, Leadership, Organization, Leaders.

Introduction

Leadership theories have always been at centre in organisational studies. It is also included in curriculum of students at senior secondary and higher education. In every institution whether educational, social, political, company, NGO or any other we will find a leader to lead it. Leadership is defined by different scholar in different way. According to Terry, "Leadership is a relationship in which one person influences others to work together willingly on related tasks to attain what the leader desires" (Terry, 1953). According to Koontz and O'Donnell, "Leadership is the process of influencing people so that they will strive willingly towards the achievement of group goals" (Koontz and O'Donnell, 1972). Scholars have given their definitions by taking different aspects of leadership. Some have considered leader as personality, some consider leadership as an attribution, some take leader as symbol, some study leader as at focus in organization, and others consider leadership as relation of influence on followers. Everyone has different perspective on definition of leadership. This is a wide concept we cannot precisely define leadership. In contemporary theories we are provided with different type of leadership like charismatic leadership, democratic leadership, transformational leadership, servant leadership, value-based leadership given by various scholar through this paper I will discuss how all this have reference in Bhagavad Gita. Bhagavad Gita consist of two words Bhagavad means 'God' and Gita means 'songs' meaning songs of God. It consists of 700 verses out of which 574 verses are spoken by lord Krishana himself (Nayak, 2018). Bhagavad Gita is conversation between Krishana and Arjuna. When arjuna is in turmoil and dropped his

weapon after seeing his kins and relative on other side in war at Kurukshetra there Krishana play role of a guider, an enabler, a driver for Arjuna. Here Arjuna is leading the clan of Pandavas and Krishana who is not here directly fought the battle but participating as 'Sarthi' of Arjuna act as leader of truth, dharma, against injustice. Krishana himself is embodiment of all things, all power, all knowledge, all Jiva are in him here in Kurukshetra battle act as king maker. In this paper we will find how Krishana have all the qualities of a leadership and how he left his legacy for future generation which still inspires us generation to generation.

Aim of study

This paper aim to find out how the styles of current leadership can be find in Bhagwad Gita. This paper also highlights how legacy of Leadership traits of Lord Krishana are available to us and act as guide for leaders.

Review of Literature

Several scholars have interpreted Bhagavad Gita with different theme. Nayak summarized the five themes of Bhagavad Gita namely Ishvara, Jiva, Prakriti, Kala, and Karma to derive the lessons of Leadership (Nayak, 2018). Roka (2011) in his book *Bhagavad Gita on Effective Leadership: Timeless Wisdom for Leaders*, makes a chapter-by-chapter analysis of the sacred text to find lessons of Bhagavad Gita. Dhulla uses Triguna theory to derive the concept of transformational leadership (Dhulla, 2014). Further concept of Me leader and We leader is derived from Bhagavad Gita by Kuknor, S.; Rastogi, S.; Singh, S.P. (2021). Satinder Dhiman in his book *Gandhi and Leadership* established how the Mahatma Gandhi's value of leadership are derived from Bhagavad Gita (Dhiman, 2015). A Bhagavad Gita linked leadership model is given by Simpson and Cunha (2021). B. Mahadevan have identifies 3 inspiring ideas of leadership (1). Strong need to lead by example (2). importance of development a high degree of equanimity (3). Understanding the principle of mutual dependence (Mahadevan, 2012) and lastly, I have reviewed The Bass Handbook of Leadership: Theory, Research and Applications by Bernard M. Bass with Ruth Bass, which is a comprehensive textbook on leadership analyses various concepts of leadership.

Methodology

This paper employs methodology of hermeneutics for analysis. Hermeneutics method means interpretation of literary text mainly ancient religious text. I have taken various slokas of Gita and interpret them to find guide for leadership.

Analysis

Charismatic Leadership in Bhagavad Gita

Charismatic Leadership concept is given by German Sociologist Max weber. It is type of leadership in which authority is derived from charisma of leader and charisma is something which is internal. The follower of leader follows him because of his charisma, his communication skills, his optimistic attitude, passionate about through mission and followers emotions, confident, compassion, self -control and monitoring etc. Krishana is wholesome of this charisma, he is everything. In Bhagavad Gita he said I am in everything, the whole knowledge, wisdom flows from me. He is followed by his followers, his devotees by his charisma. In sloka 10.20 of Bhagavad Gita Krishana said *Hey, Arjuna, I am soul located in every living heart, I am the beginning, mid and end of all. All the material which makes a human being flows from him. He is charisma of charisma. Krishana said out of twelve Aditya I am Vishnu, out of all sparking stars I am sun, out of Vedas I am Samaveda, out of all gods of heaven I am Indera, out of all senses I am mind, I am the conscience in all living beings* (10.21, 10.22). Krishana have been brought up in Gokul from his birth, he is not born as a kings son or any other famous person, yet he was son of king Vasudev but at the time of his birth he was in exile sent by his brother-in-law Kansa. In Gokul he is known by his charisma. some followed him as God, other for his attracting personality, other loves him as their life mate, and other consider him as his friend. The whole Gokul is in love with Krishana because of his Charismatic personality. After killing Kansa Krishana did not sit on throne rather, he made Ugrasen as king of Mathura. Although he was not king, yet people are devotee of Krishana because of his Charisma. In Mahabharata also Krishana is on side of Pandavas, yet he is respected by Pandavas adversaries Pitamah, Guru Dron Acharya, Guru Kripacharya, Karana, Sanjay, Vidur and all elders who know Krishana's charisma. Krishana charisma is limitless, it can even melt opponent.

Democratic Leadership in Bhagavad Gita

Democratic leadership is sometimes known as participative leadership. The idea of democratic leadership is given by Kurt Lewin. This type of leadership is founded in all the current institutions by various names like board of director, board of control, executive board, decision making group etc. they exercise their control in organization through democratic means. They are either chosen by low level employees or are appointed by the director to represent lower-level employees. It is type of leadership in which maximum participation is ensured. Democracy is not limited to participation it is wide topic it also includes right to criticize, right to oppose, right to freedom of speech and expression. Democratic leadership is not limited to decision making skills of leaders, it is way of life for leaders. It includes leader's skill of taking marginalized to mainstream,

listening demands of followers, taking a balanced decision. Democracy is about considering demands of everyone and reconcile the interest of every group in society. These things have reference in Bhagavad Gita. Krishana as leader gives his view on life, knowledge, death, soul, conscience, nature, Purusha, Karma, and everything and it is up to the listener whether to take it or not. He can also question what Krishana have said, listener can also criticize Krishana's opinion. The reader can also have opposite view to what Krishana have said. He has not mentioned any corrosion or punishment for not following what he said. Krishana in 18.63 said that *I have told you (Arjuna) all secret knowledge, mediate on it thoroughly and then do whatever you want*. This is what the essence of democracy. Individual have freedom to take what is given or he can forbid it. Here Krishana told Arjuna that I have provided you all the knowledge which exists in the world, which exists in me and now here is on Arjuna whether to consider it or not, what he wants to do his choice. Lord Krishana have not forced him to fight it is the decision of Arjuna himself to fight the War of Mahabharata which happened in Kurukshetra. Here lays the greatness of Krishana a democratic leader. Narendra Modi on launching ceremony of Swami Chidbhavananda's kindle version of Bhagavad Gita said, "Anybody who is inspired by Gita will always be compassionate by nature, democratic in temperament". Leaders such as Swami Vivekananda, Mahatma Gandhi all are democratic in their working, spirit and they are inspired by teachings of Bhagavad Gita.

Transformational Leadership in Bhagavad Gita

The concept of transformational leadership is given by Downton (1973) and further theorized by James MacGregor Burns in 1978 and the concept is further elaborated by Bernard M. Bass. According to Burns transformational leadership is "when one or more persons engage with others in such a way that leaders and followers raise one another to higher levels of motivation and morality." Transformational leadership is kind of leadership that causes change and advancement in individual and organization. It is kind of leadership in which leader's behaviour influences followers and inspires, motivates them to do extra efforts beyond their capabilities. Transformational leadership is concerned with four I's i.e., inspirational motivation, idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration (Bass, Riggio, 2006). Inspirational motivation is motivation given by leader in such a way that followers or employees of organization consider vision off their organization as their vision. Leadership motivates them in such a way that employees will have mission mindset. Leadership does this by giving example, by communication skills etc. Idealized influence includes the positive influence of leader on the employees. It is based on trust and respect and this trust and respect can be gained through respecting employees condition, their demands etc. the leader who not only works for organizational profit but also for employees well can create idealized influence. Intellectual stimulation includes challenging status quo and growing by learning. Focus of work or project should not be what will be outcome rather it should be growing and learning so that it can remove the fear factor from minds oof employees. Individualized consideration includes giving every employee a sense of ownership in goals of company and independence in their workplace. Transformational leader doesn't take decision from centre rather consider good of team. It is like decentralising the decision-making power so that employees also feel being included in it and their professional development can be assured. Transformational leadership is concept of 'we' leader rather than 'me' leader (Kuknor, Rastogi and Singh, 2021)

There is difference in transactional leadership and transformational leadership. Transactional leadership use the policy of carrot and stick. It has somewhat negative connotation while transformational leadership is positive in its aspect. It is concerned about positive change in individual behaviour and in organization.

Lord Krishana is a perfect example of transformational leader. In early phase of his life, he lived in Gokul where his father Nanda belongs to Yadava tribe, he has saved the tribe from Kansa indirect attacks (Kansa send demon to kill Krishana). Later when he moved to Mathura, he have saved his father who belongs to Vrishni clan and made Ugrasena as king of Mathura. Later he has established Dwarka as a flourishing kingdom. He also helped Pandavas in escaping from trap of Duryodhana in form of Laksa Graha and saved Draupadi from insulting and when the time for battle of Mahabharata came Krishana have dictated Bhagavad Gita to Arjuna and enable him to fight the battle of Kurukshetra to establish Dharma or righteousness (Here Dharma does not signify a particular religion, Dharma here signifies righteousness). Now we see that whether it his stepfather's clan, his father's clan, his friend's clan i.e., Pandavas clan, wherever Krishana leads he have transformed it through his intellectual stimulation, idealized influence. So, what we discuss today about transformational leadership have all the reference in Bhagavad Gita. The reference of transformational leadership in Bhagavad Gita is based on inside-outside approach i.e., from self-learning to outside learning, from self-knowing to outside knowing, form self-knowledge to outside knowledge. It has discussed Triguna theory of Transformational leadership which are Sattva, Rajas, and Tamas later which have taken by Samkhya Yoga (Dhulla, 2014).

Servant Leadership in Bhagavad Gita

The concept of 'Servant Leadership' was first popularized by Robert K. Greenleaf in his essay "The Servant as Leader" published in 1970. In simple words servant leadership means that the leader should 'serve' the follower. Greenleaf provided two premises to establish relation between leader and serving. First is 'I serve because I am the leader' and second is 'I am the leader because I serve' (Greenleaf, 1970). According to him the first premise gives selfless service of the leader but the second one includes selfishness of one who is serving because he desires to be a leader. In servant leadership leader does not want the credit of his service, he serves because he intended to serve.

According to Hindu mythology the purpose of birth of God in his different incarnation on Earth like Varaha, Mohini, Rama, Narshimha, Matsya, Krishana, Kurma, Vamana, Kalki all for serving humanity. Krishana in Bhagavad Gita serves to Arjuna and whole humanity, the whole knowledge embedded in him also Krishana have never asked for any credit for his work. His role in Battle of Kurukshetra is always as to servant. He himself took the role of chariot-driver of Kurukshetra to serve his follower (Arjuna is friend of Krishana as well as devotee of him). Also, before the Battle of Kurukshetra when Krishana was sent as ambassador in the court of Kauravas, he at urge of Pandavas leader Yudhistir immediately say yes for serving. We have other references as well from Krishana life of serving his devotee and his follower like when he is in Gokul, he serves Gokulvasi from Kaliya Naag, Bakasura, Aghasura, Vatsasura, Putna etc. Also, from Indira by lifting Govardhan mountain on his little finger. When he went to Mathura, he killed demon Kansha and saved and served his devotees from evil of Kansha.

Value -based Leadership in Bhagavad Gita

In Bhagavad Gita the most supreme value as a leader we get is the value of Righteousness. Krishana have established this value through guiding arjuna to fight for the right or dharma. The most popular song of Bhagavad Gita "*yada yada hi dharmasya glanir bhavati Bharata abhyutthānam adharmasya tadātmānam śrijāmyaham*" (4.7). In this Sloka Krishana purpose of incarnation on earth is stated as to establish Dharma or the righteousness. the other value associated with Krishana are peaceful and calm mind, egoless behaviour, fearlessness, self-knowledge, a guider, a good friend and many more.

Conclusion

Bhagavad Gita always serves in our life in every problem. This paper is only about the leadership trait, so I have taken modern forms of leadership and how these have references in Bhagavad Gita as well. If we further research on Bhagavad Gita, we will find more. It is Document full of knowledge, mysticism, spiritualism etc. Today's leadership required all the qualities which Lord Krishana poses like taking marginalized section in mainstream, balancing the interest of all section also balancing own interest with that of people, taking environment in consideration which is need of hour, and all that are explained in this paper. So, Bhagavad Gita is source of knowledge of everything, yet this document is criticized by different scholars. In Indian legacy we have a staunch critique of Bhagavad Gita is Dr B.R. Ambedkar. He considers this document as weapon of exploiting the lower class or 'Shudra' by the upper classes. In west we receive criticism about the mysticism and spiritualism of Bhagavad Gita. This document has no scientific base but the philosophical ground it holds signifies its validity in present as well in coming times.

End Note: The language used in this paper is simple and can be understand by a layman. The Slokas from Bhagavad Gita have been mentioned in x.y form where x- Chapter number and y is sloka number.

Acknowledgement This Paper have been presented in National Conference on Bhagavad Gita: Explorations Into World Literature organized by the Department of Humanities and Social Sciences , National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra, Haryana on August 25, 2023.

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